

BENEFITS OF MUSIC THERAPY ON WOMENS HEALTH

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Abstract : Music is such an art form that conveys emotions and perceptions even without using a language. The research activities focusing on the effects of art forms on health and well-being has been evidently increasing over the past two decades. Music therapy is a widely accepted and popular form for improving health through arts. Studies have shown that women being more sensitive and sentimental can be influenced more easily by music.

Key words : Music, Music therapy, Women's health, Classical Music, health benefits

INTRODUCTION: Stress is a risk factor for the onset and progression of a range of physical and emotional problems, such as cardiovascular diseases, cancers, anxiety disorders, depression. Music therapy is specially characterized by using the specific qualities of music in a therapeutic relationship with a music therapist. Music therapy involves using a person's responses and connections to music to encourage positive changes in mood and overall well-being. It can decrease anxiety and improve self-esteem. Music can also be a beneficial as listening to music, and music therapy encourages people to actively create the music they find helpful to them. This article is an attempt to review and analyze the effect of music in female physiology and pathology and its role in preservation of women's health.

HISTORY AND ORIGIN OF MUSIC THERAPY: Music has been a part of human life for thousands of years. Music has been used for treatment purposes since the earliest times. A scientific basis for music therapy only emerged after world war II and the term "music therapy" was introduced in about 1950. A scientific basis for music therapy only emerged after world war II the first program of music therapy was formulated in U.S.A in 1892.

DEFINITION OF MUSIC THERAPY : Music therapy aims to provide physical and mental benefit. Music therapy as one of the many elements of planned operations directed at re humanization of contemporary life by multilateral use of different forms of music for protecting and restoring human health and effecting a positive influence on the environment, in which a human being lives and is active, as well as on interpersonal relations in it. Music therapy is an established health care profession that uses music to address physical, emotional, cognitive and social needs of individuals of all ages. Music therapy interventions can be designed to promote wellness, manage stress, alleviate pain, express feelings, memory, improve communications and promote physical rehabilitations. On applying music therapy to reduce pre-and post-operations stress, in insomnia and different kinds of pain. These kinds of therapy also implemented prisons and approved schools.

SIGNIFICANCE OF MUSIC THERAPY : Music therapy has been studied in various contexts , including hospice and palliative care, and disabilities. How music Therapy can be used as a supportive and creative method of treating psychosocial-related impacts of cancer disease, It can be effective in reducing depression and anxiety disorders.

WHAT IS MUSIC THERAPY: Music therapy uses music to achieve individualized goals. It is an evidence - based therapy that has been well-established in the health community. Music therapy can help reduce negative stress and burden, improve mood and self-expression, and provide a non-verbal outlet for emotions. Music therapy experiences may include listening, singing, playing instruments, or composing music, and one does not need any musical skills or talents to participate.

MUSIC CAN HELP MENTAL HEALTH: Music therapy is shown to be able to help people with many different kinds of mental health problems such as anxiety, stress and minor cases of depressions. Music therapy is known as an alternative technique therapy. Music is an incredible vehicle to help us process negative emotion. Listening to music can be therapeutic when we are dealing with stress and anger. Music therapy is the unique application of music to enhance personal lives by creating positive changes in human behavior.

THE BENEFITS OF MUSIC THERAPY ON WOMEN'S HEALTH : Music is such an art form that conveys emotions and perceptions even without using a language. Music therapy is a widely accepted and popular form for improving health through arts. Music plays a significant role in improving the health and wellbeing of a female both in preventive and therapeutic aspects.

Music has been a part of human life .Stress is a risk factor for the onset and progression of a range of physical and emotional problems, such as anxiety, depression.

Music therapy is specially characterized by using the specific qualities of music in a therapeutic relationship with a music therapist. Music listing is strongly associated with stress reduction by the decrease of physiological problems. Music can also reduce negative emotions,

In Carnatic music composer saint Tyagaraja sang some incidental songs also. Ex – Raga- Deepakam – Kalala nerchina – Tyagaraja sang this raga deepakam automatically all lights are turned on.

Now a days especially women are doing lot of works because of that they need some relaxation through listening or singing music. Music research has shown that listening to music with a slow tempo or instrumentation can put people at ease and calm down even during highly stress full or painful event.

MENTAL DIMENSIONS OF WOMEN'S HEALTH: When talking about the dimensions of women's health, mental health is one of the most important. Although this is a gender stereotype, women are natural caretakers. They give so much of themselves to others that there's nothing left for them A woman who falls under this description is not living a mentally healthy life. She needs to be able to recognize that it's ok to say no- that it's ok to set boundaries.

IMPACT OF MUSIC THERAPY ON EMOTIONAL WELLBEEING OF WOMEN: Marital ties and family relationships constitute a major and an important basis on which an individual progress and success in his total life is reflected. Women mostly have to find their fulfilment for their life only in material and family setting. Music is rightly styled the language of emotions and music can play a vital role in shaping the human personality at different levels, and in different life situations. It can definitely play a very effective role in handling stressful people.

MUSIC THERAPY ON PREGNANT WOMEN : Stress and anxiety during pregnancy have been associated with premature and low birth weight babies, presumably through fetus over exposition to glucocorticoids. Hower, medication for stress may carry risks to the expectant mother. A relaxing intervention as hart as 30 minutes, especially listening to music decreases plasma cortisol and self-reported state anxiety score. Pregnant women might benefit from the routine practice of relaxation in the imminence of clinical stressful events. Listening to music during pregnancy contributes to be better sense of well-being and less pronounced symptoms of postpartum depression. Symptoms evidence confirms the effects of music therapy on the level of stress and anxiety in pregnant women.

MUSIC THERAPY AND SELF-CARE : Music therapy is a form of therapy that uses music to achieve individualized goals such as reducing stress, improving mood, self-expression. Music therapy can be used in various ways for self-care, including writing, drawing to music, playing an instrument, listening to music, singing, and attending music therapy session.

Listening to music can be a form of self-care and can help individuals to relax and reduce stress. It can also be a way to improve mood and promote positive emotions. Singing can be a form of self-care and can help individuals, aiming to accomplish various therapeutic objectives.

MUSIC THERAPY AND MENTAL HEALTH: Mental health diseases such as depression and anxiety can have devastating consequences both for patients and their families. Music can improve symptoms associated with mental illness, but it can provide an environment for social interaction. Music therapy helps the individual to express emotions while producing a state of mental relaxation, and consequently it can be beneficial in decreasing symptoms of depression and anxiety, while enhancing interpersonal relationship.

FUTURE DIRECTION OF MUSIC THERAPY : The field of music therapy is constantly evolving, and there are several trends to expect in the coming years. The popularity of music therapy as an effective treatment for various psychological conditions has been on the rise, indicating a growing demand for therapists in this field. Music technology instruments have been employed in collaborative efforts for mental well-being, and they have also been harnessed to enhance communication and social aptitude in individuals with autism.

RAGAS AND ITS EFFECTS OF MUSIC THERAPY:

1. Raga Hamsadhvani: Evokes sweet, deep, cloudy and stable state of mind and prevents acidity.
2. Raga Todi: give tremendous relief to patients of high blood pressure.
3. Raga Ananda bhairavi: suppresses stomach pain in both men and women. Control blood pressure.
4. Raga Bhairavi: reduces anxiety, pressure, skin disease, allergies.
5. Raga Kalyani: gives energy and removes tension and acts as general tonic.

CONCLUSION: Music has the power to evoke various emotions and can have a therapeutic effect on individuals. Music therapy is a recognized health care discipline designed to assist individuals facing challenges in social, physical, mental and emotional domains. Music is the best option to live stress and tension free life. It is true that some kind of emotional and psychological risk which does not give stability to the mind, body and mood. Music is the only source that minimizes the emotional and psychological risk for woman.

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Dear Sir / Madam,

I, Dr T. Girija Seshamamba have read and agreed to the content of the submitted article and wish to submit an original research article entitled

“BENEFITS OF MUSIC THERAPY ON WOMEN’S HEALTH”

for consideration by ShodhKosh. I confirm that this work is original and has not been published elsewhere, nor it is currently under consideration for publication elsewhere.

A rectangular box containing a handwritten signature in black ink. The signature reads "T. Girija Seshamamba" in a cursive script.